

Question raised by requestor

First question: Can an antifreeze product containing solely glycerin – which is an authorised feed material in the EU – be legally used in animals' drinking water during transport to prevent freezing? If not, what legal basis do authorities have for sanctioning this practice?

Second question: The product Reidal, produced in the Netherlands, is increasingly being used by transporters in animals' drinking water. While glycerin is an authorised feed material in the EU and may be administered to animals dissolved in drinking water, certain views suggest that this practice is not acceptable, as water containing glycerin does not adequately quench the feeling of thirst.

Answer

Definitions

For the purpose of this Q2E, the definitions of 'glycerol', 'crude glycerine', 'glycerine', 'feed materials' and 'feed additives' shall apply.

Glycerol	Pure substance of Propane-1,2,3-triol, $C_3H_8O_3$;
Crude glycerine/glycerine	Co-product/product of i) oil/fat splitting, ii) the production of biodiesel, and iii) saponification of oil/fats containing impurities like mineral or organic salts, matter organic non glycerol, methanol [1];
Feed materials	Products of vegetable or animal origin, whose principal purpose is to meet animals' nutritional needs, in their natural state, fresh or preserved, and products derived from the industrial processing thereof, and organic or inorganic substances, whether or not containing feed additives, which are intended for use in oral animal-feeding either directly as such, or after processing, or in the preparation of compound feed, or as carrier of premixtures [2];
Feed additives	Substances, micro-organisms or preparations, other than feed material and premixtures, which are intentionally added to feed or water in order to perform, in particular, one or more of the functions mentioned in Article 5(3) of Regulation (EC) No 1831/2003 [3]; specified later in the text.

Properties and application of glycerol

Glycerol is a trivalent sugar alcohol that exists as a colourless, odourless, sweet-tasting, viscous liquid at 0 °C and normal atmospheric pressure and is miscible with water. It may be sourced naturally from plants or animals (from oils or fats) or synthetically. Glycerol has become readily available as a by-product of the biodiesel industry and is sometimes used as a glucogenic substrate to replace corn or corn-based energy-rich feed materials [4,5]. Its application as a feed material has been extensively studied in ruminant and non-ruminant animals [5,6] and since glycerol is a natural metabolite resulting from digestion, it is generally considered as harmless [7]. It is assumed that adding up to 15 % crude glycerine to the diet of ruminants and up to 10 % to that of monogastric animals has no detrimental effect on animal health, even in the presence of the major impurities such as methanol or sodium [8]. However, depending on its source and production technique, other contaminants may be present in (crude) glycerine, which may pose a hazard to animals or humans. This is particularly relevant when category 1 animal by-products, i.e. highest risk material of animal origin that are not fit for human consumption such as dead pet or zoo animals or the body (parts) of animals containing specified risk material, are used in biodiesel production [8].

Due to its miscibility with water, glycerol is used as an antifreeze. The achievable freezing-point depression depends on the mixing ratio with water (Table 1).

Table 1: Achievable freezing-point depression at different mixing ratios of glycerol and water [9].

Glycerol by weight percent	Water percent	Freezing points [°C]
0	100	0
10	90	-1.6
20	80	-4.8
30	70	-9.5
40	60	-15.4
50	50	-23.0

Legal framework

The Community Catalogue of feed materials according to Article 24 of Regulation (EC) No 767/2009 [2] was established with Commission Regulation (EU) No 68/2013 [1]. The Catalogue lists feed materials in a non-exhaustive manner. According to the latter regulation, crude glycerine and glycerine are listed as a feed material (13.8.1 Glycerine, crude and 13.8.2 Glycerine). No maximum levels are set for the use of glycerine as a feed material.

Regulation (EC) No 1831/2003 on additives for use in animal nutrition establishes a Community procedure for authorising the placing on the market and use of feed additives. Feed additives according to the above definition are intentionally added to feed or water in order to perform, in particular, one or more of the following functions:

1. favourably affect the characteristics of feed
2. favourably affect the characteristics of animal products
3. favourably affect the colour of ornamental fish and birds
4. satisfy the nutritional needs of animals
5. favourably affect the environmental consequences of animal production
6. favourably affect animal production, performance or welfare, particularly by affecting the gastro-intestinal flora or digestibility of feedingstuffs, or
7. have a coccidiostatic or histomonostatic effect

The Community Register of Feed Additives is publicly available at <https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/feed-additives/search>.

According to Commission Regulation (EU) No 892/2010 [10] glycerol is no longer to be considered a feed additive within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 1831/2003. Products containing glycerol as an additive were allowed to be placed on the market until 9 October 2013 and remain on the market until stocks are exhausted.

Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 [11] on the protection of animals during transport and related operations lays down in Article 3 on general conditions for the transport of animals that water, feed and rest are offered to the animals at suitable intervals and are appropriate in quality and quantity to their species and size. Further, animals shall be protected from extreme temperatures and for long journeys by road the temperature range within the means of transport shall be maintained within a range of 5 °C to 30 °C with a +/-5 °C tolerance.

Feed material 'Reidal'

According to the data sheet provided by the requestor (see Annex I) 'Reidal' is labelled as feed material for pigs, cattle and sheep and is composed of 86.5 % glycerol and the sensory additive Quinoline Yellow at 40 mg for an unspecified package size. It was put on the market for frost protection of drinking water during transport. The manufacturer's suggested dosage for this purpose is 1 part 'Reidal' to 2 parts water for a freezing-point depression to -15 °C, and 1 part 'Reidal' to 1 part water for a depression to -21 °C.

As can be inferred from Table 1, a significant amount of water would have to be replaced by glycerol to achieve a significant freezing-point depression. Following the suggested mixing ratios of 1:2 and 1:1 for the product 'Reidal' at the given concentration of 86.5 % glycerol, an animal would only consume 0.71 and 0.57 litres of water, respectively, per litre of its aqueous solution. It remains unclear if such a mixture may still be considered in alignment with Article 3 of Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 regarding the provision of water in appropriate quality and quantity during the transport of animals.

While its component glycerol is an authorised feed material for the above species, the additive Quinoline Yellow was authorised as feed additive for non food-producing animals only and the period of authorisation ended on 9 March 2025 according to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/244 of 16 February 2015 concerning the authorisation of Quinoline Yellow as a feed additive for non food-producing animals [12,13]. Thus, the formulation of 'Reidal' does not appear to be compatible with existing legislation in the EU.

Glycerol supplementation and perceived thirst

Only a little information is available on the effect of glycerol supplementation on water intake. Osbourne et al. [4] found no difference in water intake in periparturient dairy cattle when glycerine (containing 99.7 % glycerol) was supplemented at a concentration of 20 g/L in their drinking water, compared to water only. Schröder and Südekum [14] found that daily water intake was slightly higher when steers consumed mixed diets containing glycerine of low (63.3 % glycerol) and medium (85.3 % glycerol) purity, but not if glycerine of high (99.8 % glycerol) purity was used (diet formulated to contain on dry matter basis: 40 % forage, 50 % concentrate and 10 % of pure glycerol, irrespective of the purity of the glycerol-containing product). Further effects when adding glycerol or glycerine to livestock diets, such as reduced dry matter intake, reduced milk yield, or increased plasma concentration of glucose have been reported [6].

When tested in humans, self-reported ratings for perceived thirst during exercise were lowest for a 6 % carbohydrate-electrolyte beverage with 4 % glycerol and a 10 % glycerol solution compared to a 6 % carbohydrate-electrolyte beverage and a water placebo, all of similar sweetness (aspartame in water) [15]. Another study reported enhanced fluid retention and lowest post-exercise thirst in mountain bike racers who ingested glycerol at 1 g/kg body weight in aqueous solution before the exercise compared to water only (volume equal to 2.8 % body weight; this equals a glycerol concentration of approximately 36 g/kg drinking solution) [16]. Thus, the addition of glycerol to drinks may change water-balance in the body, and the sensation of thirst, at least in humans.

Conclusions

Adding glycerol to drinking water to reduce the risk of freezing during the transport of animals is covered by the definition of feed additives. Intentionally adding a substance to feed or water to favourably affect its characteristics, in this case by lowering the freezing point of water, is a technological purpose and does not serve to meet animals' nutritional needs. The authorisation of glycerol as feed additive for use in animal nutrition according to Regulation (EC) No 1831/2003 was rejected with Commission Regulation (EU) No 892/2010, however, stocks that were placed on the market before 9 October 2013 may be used up.

Securing water availability remains important for animal transport in cold climates. Minimum temperatures during transport are only provided for long journeys by road, where the temperature within the means of transport must not be below 0 °C according to Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005. Transporting animals when ambient temperatures are significantly below zero degrees, requires frost protection of the watering devices, e.g. using other means such as insulation, heating or a water circulation system. Glycerol or glycerol-containing alternatives do not appear to be a viable solution for this cause.

Although a positive effect on the water-balance of aqueous glycerol solutions has been reported in humans, this has not been investigated in livestock. Only two feeding trials in cattle used glycerol as an energy source in livestock, with no significant effect on water intake. However, these studies used glycerol at substantially lower concentrations than those suggested for its use as an antifreeze in drinking water during the transport of animals. These studies do not provide any evidence on the effectiveness of aqueous glycerol solutions in quenching the thirst of livestock.

ReiDal

Long Distance Animal Care

Voedermiddel / Einzelfuttermittel / Feed Material / Une matière première / Fodermidler

Voedermiddel voor varkens, rundvee en schapen. / Einzelfuttermittel für Schweine, Rinder und Schafe. / Feed Material for Pigs, Cattle and Sheep. / Une matière première pour des porcs, des bovins et des ovins. / Fodermidler til svin, kvaeg og far.

Samenstelling / Zusammensetzung / Composition / Composition / Sammensætning:
Glycerine, Glyzerin, Glycerine, Glycérine, Glycerin

Toevoegmiddelen / Zusatzstoffe / Additives / Additifs / Tilsætningsstoffer:

Sensorieel/ Sensorischer/ Sensory/ Sensoriel/ Sensorisk:

Quinoline Yellow -E104- 40 mg

Dosering vorstvrj houden:	1 deel Reidal op 2 delen water tot -15 C	1 deel Reidal op 1 deel water tot -21 C
Dosierung Forstschut:	1 Teil Reidal auf 2 Teile Wasser bis -15 C	1 Teil Reidal auf 1 Teil Wasser bis -21 C
Dosage frost prtction:	1 part Reidal to 2 parts of water to -15 C	1 part Reidal to 1 part of water to -21 C
Dosage contre le gel jusqu:	1 partie Reidal à 2 parties d'eau à -15 C	1 partie Reidal à 1 partie de l'eau à -21 C
Dosering frostbeskytelse:	1 del Reidal til 2 dele vand til -15 C	1 del Reidal til 1 del vand til -21 C

Aanbevolen voor het vorstvrj houden van drinkwater tijdens vervoer.

Reidal staat garant voor vorstvrj drinkwater.

Empfohlen für das frostfrei halten von Trinkwasser während des Transports.

Reidal garandeert frostfreies Trinkwasser.

Recommended for frost protection of water during transport.

Reidal guarantees frostfree drinking water.

Recommandé pour la protection contre le gel de l'eau potable pendant le transport.

Reidal assure de l'eau sans gel.

Anbefales til frostsikring af vand under transport.

Reidal garanterer frostfrit drikkevand

Analytische bestanddelen / Analytische Bestandteile / analytical constituents / les constituants analytiques / analytiske bestanddele:

Glycerol, Glyzerin, Glycerol, Glycérol, Glycerol	86,5 %
Kalium, Kalium, Potassium, Potassium, Kalium	0,0 %
Natrium, Natrium, Sodium, Sodium, Natrium	0,0 %

Bewaring: buiten direct zonlicht

Storage: out of direct sunlight

Opbevaring: i direkte sollys

Lagerung: vor direkter Sonneneinstrahlung schützen

Conservation: à l'abri de la lumière directe du soleil

Produced by GMP / HACCP guidelines
Reg. no 001219

Produced: See barcode
Best before: See barcode

Reg Nr:
40120

exportwegerij
Gebr. Reimink b.v.

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